

Research Article

Multiversal Consciousness: The Peer, the Point of Reference, and the Meme

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Abstract

As we think of, hear about or imagine the objective existence of multiple universe(s), the multiverse, our individual brain-confined consciousness scratches this multiversal consciousness and creates a powerful meme for all flag-bearers of consciousness. We bring the endless sky within our brain. This sets the 'standard' for investigation of consciousness within and outside the head letting different kinds of boundaries to disappear with 'precision'. These boundaries are the layers of our mind. Consciousness has no boundary. Excessive mind activity is a spoiler of peace for the neurons. Consciousness, however, is neuroprotective and so also the dreamless sleep. Their relationship has also been explored in this article.

Keywords: The Multiversity, Cognitive Faculty, Natural Neuroprotective Mechanisms, Mechanism of Sleep

Introduction

Modern enterprise of science for the past three hundred years has thought of the universe as a singular number. Everything in science has revolved around this one universe. The universe is our cortical cognitive construct. None of us has seen the universe, or its boundary. The mystics, whose seamless consciousness operates from outside the brain, and some of the astrophysicists on the other hand, however, communicated in their own way that there are multiple universe(s) [1, 2, 3]. We live in one of them. Multiverse is the plural of singular universe. As individuals, the mystics love pluralism without compromising individualism and are not in a conflict with brain-confined consciousness. Multiple universe(s) form a system, intellectually comprehensible, the largest system which may be called "The Multiversity". When several science treatises, papers, and mathematics are engaged in discussion or investigation of multiple universe(s), consciousness in human brains have started scratching the multiversal consciousness. General public and delicate young minds being aware of the existence of multiple universe(s) from science papers or mystic's stories have started breaking the boundary, and on the basis of their imagination are for an unparalleled cognitive journey from earthly planetary consciousness to stellar consciousness, galactic consciousness, universal consciousness for a final peer into the inter-universal essence or the multiversal consciousness. In the parliament of multiple universe(s), multiversal consciousness is the Prime Minister that organizes the legislation of laws of universal freedom for every universe to follow.

Let us begin consciousness research afresh with this multiversal consciousness as the peer or the 'standard' for calibrating our individual consciousness accurately. Also, use this multiversal consciousness as the point of reference or the 'control' for achieving precision in the laboratory of consciousness research. Remember, multiversal consciousness is now a widely spreading meme for humanity in the advanced institutes of human culture. No doubt we are heading towards an unprecedented quality of

cognitive evolution.

There are several boundaries to cross. The boundaries are nothing but our layers of minds! Mind divides consciousness. Although almost all of the contents of the human mind become untraceable at the level of intergalactic hyperspace, the human mind finally dissolves with the dissolution of the boundary of the cerebral cortex at the boundary of the universe. While returning to earth, new boundaries form, and new intentions catch up within the brain.

Consciousness is boundless but never sleeps. It is never solely confined to the organ brain, which sleeps regularly. Consciousness cares for this valuable organ to express itself as what it is, and what are its operational mechanics. Strategically, it is easier to do a science for consciousness than to do a science of consciousness. The former accommodates multiverse, dark energy, exotic matters, scalar fields and subtle energy at the top level, information states, the psychic faculty and their respective operation at the centre, and the space, time, matter and energy at the bottom. Also, while investigating consciousness from the periphery there is a lot to learn from a single biological cell, which without any brain-like structure behaves as multiheaded [4,5]. On the basis of its own choice from available options, the cell learns, and makes conscious decisions by its 'will'.

The brain, although, has been mistakenly considered the source of consciousness, it is not! There is no evidence for it. On the other hand, there is evidence that consciousness operates from outside the brain [6]. Consciousness, for its complete manifestation also calls for multilevel integrity of this brain. One can do science on the development of this series of classical integrity, quantum integrity, phenomenological integrity at the elementary level, and integrity to behave transmissive for multiversal consciousness.

Regarding this multiverse there are views of scientists, mystics and humanists. None of them has observed the multiverse.

Initially the existence of multiple universe(s) could only be an object of imagination. The axiology of imagination is, however, made intelligible by the support of mathematics. Mathematicians such as Max Tegmark [7] and a few others have predicted such an existence, and even classified them. The possibility of the existence of an intelligible multiverse becomes stronger should we get a hint of it from the use of distant space telescopes placed on space flights. With such a possibility, the chance of verifiability becomes bright! To bring down imagination to a verifiable state is, however, a function of a 'transmissive' brain.

Since Einstein's acceptance of the zero-point energy state as cosmological constant, classical physics have stood still. With the arrival of the idea of the multiverse, physical science might take zero-point energy fluctuations as an opening for deep cosmology through quantum discontinuity along the lines of subquantum and sub-subquantum nests of nature. Some of us are thinking of a continuity of ZPE fluctuations with the space science of interstellar, intergalactic and inter-universal space. To investigate this frontier of science, the basic requirement is the investigator's brain to be in a cool ZPE state, as suggested in [8].

The mystics describe contentless and unconditional consciousness in the Essence from which several universe(s) generate and undergo dissolution. In this dynamic essence, the mystics identify Mother Nature as the kinetic pole, executive front, mobile facets of consciousness. Mother nature is the nature from which the rest of nature has originated. From the unity of Consciousness-Mother Nature is supposed to originate the Multiversal musical code sourcing, according to the author, the subtle energy as Conf-E-C (Conformon equivalent of consciousness), Phot-E-C (Photon equivalent of consciousness), Phon-E-C (Phonon equivalent of consciousness), and Neut-E-C (Neutrino equivalent of consciousness).

Humanists never find in this *essence* any possibility of war, fight, conflict or disturbance of any kind and declare it as the immortal eternal infinite landscape of Ananda, bliss and peace, where individualism does not interfere with the growth of pluralism, and pluralism encourages individualism.

Consciousness

Consciousness, non-observable but the most influential 'entity', is both non-discrete as per e.g., neurologist John Huglings Jackson (1835-1911) and discrete (e.g., Francis Crick, Gerald Edelman, Antonio Damasio etc.). It has a ground part and an operational part (may also be called Mother nature) which is the executive front of ground consciousness. The 'unity' property of consciousness is in its non-discrete ground part that accounts for its ability to make a will or 'won't. Other two properties of consciousness, 'subjectivity' and 'intentionality', present latent in the ground part but are expressed in consciousness's operational part as discrete systems property of cognition and feeling (expressed in behavior as emotion). Once discretized, will-making property is handed over to the system's chief, the CEO of consciousness within the system, the 'self'. Will, Cognition and Feeling (Emotion) are, therefore, three functional identities of consciousness.

The governance of the system multiple universe(s) emanates from this ground consciousness, which is homogeneously present all over the space overarching the entire multiverse as a ground without any background. The operational consciousness as an executive front of ground consciousness takes care of all system universe(s).

The will-making ability of consciousness is observed in all conscious entities and systems irrespective of their size, starting from a unicellular or-

ganism to the world leaders asserting their political will, to the intellectually comprehensible largest systems of the Multiversity. Manifestation of feeling (emotion) and cognitive ability depends on several factors within the system.

The primal "will" of consciousness had been supposed to be for its manifestation from royal monistic status towards plurality. From what we have labelled as the essence of the Multiversity, several universe(s) originate. The universe does not originate from the Big Bang, but is described to originate through a silent information-split phenomenon [9]. Dark energy is information-sourced. How information is created from the "will" of consciousness and then converted into a signal has also been described by the author [10]. The brain offers the supporting organ structures for the cognitive faculty to convert the "will" of consciousness into a sensible signal for the 4-D world.

Cognitive Faculty

Consciousness cannot be explained by neural science alone. It requires psychological science too. Expanding on these lines, the author develops the concept of system psyche, its structure, operation and possible molecular links [11,12]. The operative part of consciousness is mostly expanded as 'psyche'. With creation of duality or plurality, operative consciousness, the first faculty of cognitive orchestra appoints a CEO for the newly created system as 'self'. Consciousness and 'self' are identical in substance. Consciousness gets the work done by its CEO, the 'self', for the system. With creation of duality, the boundary between the two systems matures as the faculty of "*mind*". The mind is the organ of communication between two conscious systems. The operational field of the mind extends from the boundary of the universe to the boundary of the 4-D world at zero-point energy state or fluctuations. The mind conceives information, with a command to deliver a 'form' from *information's* inside. The components of form are space and time. The delivery is accompanied by release of energy observed as fluctuation of energy at the level of ZPE. The mind is the final common pathway from and to the cognitive world, to and from the 4-D world. What we understand as '*life*' has a gross part and an intangible part. The intangible parts of '*life*' have representation in the system psyche. This representation is vital in cognition, without which there is neither feeling nor qualia, nor even memory formation [13]. Intangible life might operate across ZPE states/fluctuations. The 'self' cannot manufacture memory, qualia and feeling. The mind too. Even consciousness alone cannot do it. According to the author it can be done only by the '*life*' in the composite system of the psyche. Consciousness, self, intangible parts of '*life*', mind and information are five faculty members of the systems psyche, or cognitive orchestra.

How to identify these non-localizable, non-observable psychic faculty? It is possible by identifying their specific operation. Consciousness is identified by its 'will'-making property and the self by its executive power of implementing conscious decisions with flawless logic. The intangible parts of '*life*' offer logistic, maintains homeostasis, makes qualia and generates feeling. The presence of mind could be identified from the operation of making a signal out of a piece of information for the exterior 4-D world and also for converting the signals from the 4-D world into pieces of information for the interior cognitive world. Interestingly, the cognitive faculty can work with or without a brain or brain-like structure (reference number 4 and 5). At this point we note that AI built up on the basis of ANN technology, which has no life, cannot have functions like the system psyche or cognitive orchestra!

The hierarchy and administration of the cognitive faculty are discussed later in this paper.

The Brain

The brain is an organ of one hundred billion neurons and several hundred billions of glial cells consisting of astrocytes (which make tripartite synapses with neurons), myelin-making oligodendroglia, and microglia as the glial counterpart of the immune cell.

Three parts of the brain are vital to make us conscious [14]; the cerebral cortex (often called the 'executive suit'), the brainstem, and their connecting link, the reticular system traversing through thalamus (often called the 'bridge chamber'). The reticular system involves the central grey core neurons of the neuraxis including thalami, where neurons hardly form any network, but just fall short of making a syncytium! In neuroscience of consciousness, we come across papers with emphasis on the unique role of each of the three parts in the genesis of brain-confined conscious states, e.g., papers on the cerebral cortex especially lateral frontal and temporal lobes (<https://www.mpg.de/8425992/seat-of-consciousness>), papers on the brain stem [15,16], and papers on the thalamus [17,18]. Hydranencephaly patients have little cortex. Several of the patients who are uncon-

scious in vegetative state have thalamic lesions and reticular system injury. The brainstem holds all important cardiac center, vasomotor center and respiratory centers along with spinal incoming fibres, which offer inputs to its reticular system. A little trauma on this brainstem makes the person lose consciousness.

The brain as an organ has evolved as (i) the "home" and workplace for the cognitive faculties, (ii) a sensor of different information states, and (iii) a biological device for expression of behavior of consciousness.

(i) The brain and the Psyche

As an organ, the brain accommodates the cognitive faculty within it for their operation with different neural oscillations, waves, networks and wi-fi connections. The details of the mechanism of this local connectivity with the nonlocal elements is yet to be worked out. The author has suggested geometry of different information states to connect locally acting players such as space, time, matter and energy with nonlocal players such as consciousness, self, 'life' and mind (figure 1).

Figure 1. Begin your observation with the central horizontal axis of the figure, with the words in blue in capital letters. On the left side, it begins with the signal, followed by Information, Knowledge, Experience, and at the extreme right side ends with Wisdom. In terms of knowledge, these milestones have been represented respectively by data/factual knowledge, informative knowledge, formative knowledge, transformative knowledge, and sublime knowledge. On the topmost line, the figure describes the same milestones in the language of information-science, starting with space-time construct of information, followed by non-digitized information, non-factorizable information (where three folia of information, namely content, intent and the ability to reduce uncertainty, could not be separately identified, and several related information are in a combinatorial symmetry), information manifold, and information crystal. In the perspective of Informatics-Neuroscience, signals lead to sensation, information to perception, knowledge to concept formation and hypothesis generation, and experience to theory, and wisdom to Worldview formation. Stretched over the five landmarks/milestones, there are four operations expressed numerically from the left to right, as Operations I, II, III, and IV conducted by the non-observable but influential operators. In popular language of the formative world, Operator I of the natural world is known as 'Mind', Operator II of the natural world has been mystically labelled as 'Self' in the formal world, Operator III of the natural world is called 'Life' in the formal world, and the Operator IV in both scientific and spiritual terms of natural and formal worlds are labelled as Consciousness.

Bottom-up, cerebral-extracerebral communication happens when a) any sensation, perception, and conceptual development leads to conscious experience, b) the person is consciously dreaming, imagining, and playing with pure intention, and c) the person takes a leap in faith, devotion and love.

Top down, extracerebral-cerebral communication happens when the brain behaves in a transmissive way either a) consciously, converting the un-

known to imagination, imagination to intelligible, intelligible to possible, and the possible to verifiable state, or b) during non-conscious happenings of intuition, illumination and revelation. It is worthwhile to understand the skeleton of this top-down route as shown below.

The same cognitive faculties are involved in conversion of consciousness's will into signals in the 4-D world (figure 2). Both figures 1 & 2 are taken from my earlier published papers, e.g., [10, 19].

Figure 2. The left side of the figure describes the structural framework of the ontological operators with their phase position. The right side shows the functional outline of the operations from the 'will' to the event. In absence of any known force, field or visible energy consciousness operates with only 'will', that originates from the ground consciousness and is converted into intention by its operative facet (also called Mother Nature). Self's operation examines the logic and ethical part of intention while the 'life'-operation takes care of the aesthetic part of its execution along with the logistics of energy-homeostasis. Instruction sheet, thus formed, is handed over to the event-making entity, the 'mind' for occurrence of events in the 4-D world. The result is creation of new space, new time, and new tangible energy within the neural substrate of cognition. This last operation happens across ZPE in the natural world, and for behavioral expression captures the neural network and Wi-fi operative in the ZPE state of the brain.

There could be a debate on the topic whether theories do or do not originate from the 'sky' [20]. However, formulation of a theory from an experience irrespective of its sensory, intuitive, illuminative, or revelatory origin, requires cerebral-extracerebral communication, a communication of the brain with the sky. This communication helps the new theory to connect with the good existing theories. The science progresses vertically only this way.

(ii) The Brain as a sensor

Evidence has been emerging that favors the brain as a 'sensor' of different information states [21]. This also gets strengthened from an observation [22, 23] in clinical set up that the neurons in the brain can detect patterns without conscious thought.

(iii) The Brain as Transmissive

We have mentioned the situations when the brain behaves as a communicator of the infinite sky. When the brain-confined consciousness communicates with multiversal consciousness, the earth gets a chance to watch a few glimpses of the multiversal behaviors.

Natural neuroprotective Mechanisms

In search of natural neuroprotective mechanisms, I find two important ones ingrained in our body system. The first one is contentless consciousness and the other one is deep sleep. Deep sleep state is the absolute resting phase of the brain, and is one of the ZPE states of the brain. Brain-vacuum interaction is natural in this phase (see reference no 8). Excessive mind activities spoil the peace for the neurons. Consciousness, however, is neuroprotective. In this context we discuss these two natural neuroprotective mechanisms ingrained within our biological system; A. Sleep and B. Consciousness. Dreamless sleep is neuroprotective and therefore in absence of its adequacy, there is neuro-irritation and even neurodegeneration. Consciousness in its native form is considered ever a healer.

A. SLEEP

Sleep is a consciousness-phenomenon. Sleep is not a multiversal, universal, galactic, stellar or planetary phenomenon, although each one of them influences sleep. The planets are observable from the satellite, the stars from the spaceflights, the galaxies through long distance telescopes. The universe and the multiverse are our cortical intellectual constructs. A system cannot sleep keeping its observables online and constructions alive!

The phenomenon of sleep begins when the system turns towards the Essence of the Multiversity, which in simple language is called consciousness.

The phenomenon of sleep cannot be understood without understanding the depth psychology; the hierarchy and operations of the cognitive faculty. As perception cannot alter the fundamentals of different information states, so experience cannot change the most fundamentals. Most fundamentals are the cognitive faculty and their operations.

The Administration and Hierarchy of Cognitive faculty

Their administration is as follows (Figure 3). The mind is the final common contact of the psyche with the 4-D world. The mind reports to 'self', the CEO of consciousness for the system. The self and 'life' (the intangible parts) maintain a tangled hierarchy between them, and independently report to operative consciousness.

From the 4-D neural world of the brain (somatosensory, proprioceptive and viscerosensory), the mind collects signals and converts them into different pieces of information. Loads on the mind are arranged in four layers. From superficial to deep, the layers are of (i) information (ii) thoughts (iii) dreams during sleep, and imagination when awake, and at the depth (iv) the intents. Intents are derived from intention coming from operative consciousness. Intention is generated from the 'will' of ground consciousness. Intention is converted into intent after analysis of its logic by the 'self' and logistic by the intangible parts of 'life'. Both 'self' and 'life' operate from the nest deeper than the mind. The 'life' is also responsible for the production of qualia, memory, and generation of feeling that is conveyed to the mind to generate emotional expression in the 4-D world of the brain.

The phenomenon of Sleep

On the basis of information in the mind received from proprioception, viscerosensory or physical sensory signals in the tune that the 'manifestation

machine', the organ brain, requires rest, or on the basis of consciousness's own 'will' to shut down the machine for a while, consciousness's permissive 'will' is converted into 'intention' to sleep by operative consciousness and is passed as intent to the mind after scrutiny by 'self' and 'life'. Falling asleep is then dissociating mind operations from neural operation. During dream sleep the brain as a machine is under rest but the mind continues to operate alone, dissociated from the brain. Regeneration and healing may begin in the 4-D brain. Since by nature the mind is restless, it intermittently connects with the brain and we often find physical activities during dream sleep. Deprived completely of sensory stimuli when the mind itself gradually goes into rest and becomes still, the dreamless sleep begins. There is zero provocation from the 4-D world. Long term potentiation of synapses, regeneration, plasticity and healing are at their respective peaks. The great four, 'life', 'self', operative consciousness, and ground consciousness, remain awake forever. At the time when the brain and mind sleep, silent intra-system or extra-system communication between the great four takes place of which we know nothing. *Mandukhya Upanishad* describes this silent communication as 'yoganidra', a pathway to experience and understand the *Turiya* state of consciousness, the unconditional consciousness that could probably in science be described as the *Essence* of the Multiversity.

Natural awakening begins with a message from the grosser 'life' to the subtle parts of 'life', of completion of the rest. 'Life' awakens the system. If 'life' falls silent during sleep, we encounter the death phenomenon during sleep. The message of 'life' for awakening, in turn, is sent to the self and also to the mind that begins acting on the vital respiratory, cardiac and vasomotor centres in the reticular system of the brainstem. The reticular system spreads through the thalamus to the cerebral cortex. The person yawns (unconscious brain stem activity), and becomes awake with brainstem activation. With clearance of message from the thalamus to the cerebral cortex the awakened 'self' of the person rubs his eyes, sensitizes the sense organs and becomes aware of the surrounding environment. Following this supportive act, consciousness takes the role of participating, intervening, or creative consciousness from the phase of sensation to experience. Consciousness intervenes only to assert its choice, that may be creative by execution of the 'will' from the ground (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The most fundamentals in the science of consciousness are cognitive faculty, their positions, hierarchy and operations. Mind is the final common pathway to a 4-D world. Consciousness operates from the depth (nest V). Nature has been shown to have a nested structure to accommodate the cognitive faculty appropriately. Self and life operate from nest IV and mind from nest III of nature. On the right side is the caterpillar model of operative consciousness that affronts itself gradually to engage in the mind-game.

B. CONSCIOUSNESS

The relation between consciousness and the neuron is of peaceful love. Neuron-philic of consciousness and consciousness-philic of neurons have reasons in a) neuron's genome with noncoding long repetitive sequences of DNA, b) microtubular stability for infrequent or no mitosis, c) characteristic ion pumps in their cell membranes, that create ever readiness for excitability. Also, the characteristic water-laser systems, evanescent/tunnelling/tachyon-photons, condensation of such photons (instead of electrons) resulting in superconductivity within protoplasm at body temperature with superluminal velocity, are considered frontier areas in this context [24]. Love is a non-sensory 'sky' phenomenon. Love is a cortical manifestation of supracortical consciousness [25]. Dealing with the sig-

nal world happens through senses. Signals can injure, but love is always a healer. Engagement with unconditional multiversal consciousness protects neurons from the harmful effects of environmental signal networks meant for pleasing the senses.

When the cells of one's foot know that their neural representatives in the cerebral cortex have multiversal connections, then universal love manifests in one's body. When anyone 'thinks with the foot' (a management language) and his mind is immersed in multiversal consciousness, the delivery of a flawless decision is on the card. Love manifested from the multiversal consciousness is inexhaustible, with cortical limits. This love is unconditional. There could not be better therapeutics for neurons during

their growth and maturation phase, regeneration from exhausted states, and in recovery from early degenerated states.

Concluding Remarks

Have you ever experienced that the brain is not the source of consciousness? Your consciousness operates 'Out of the Head' on the brain! If yes, then you are experiencing supracortical consciousness, which the author experienced in 1984 and documented it in 1985 [25]. If it is so with you too, get out from the brainstem and basal ganglia consciousness (wakefulness, awareness, and 4-D orientation), limbic and thalamic consciousness (feeling, emotion and motivation) and cortical consciousness (self-consciousness, unified consciousness) of Paul MacLean's Triune Brain (Reptilian, Paleomammalian and Neomammalian) along with the earnings obtained from the experience of supracortical consciousness.

Travel the entire universe, the system of multiverse, *The Multiversity*, and come back on the earth to reenter your brain with the multiversal consciousness.

The travel leads to reformatting of the brain, rewiring of its neural assemblies, and reorganizing the brain's wireless connectivity. If it looks like an assumption to begin with, hold it as a great assumption! Once you succeed, you make a new beginning with a "Buddha-state of the brain" [26, also 8] towards progressive acquisition of knowledge, with new art of delivering a multiversal 'will' or 'won't' for execution of different new skills in your activities, which is surely accompanied by an empathic attitude. The descent follows three developmental lines of the cognitive, psychomotor and affective brain. In addition, there is an outpouring of creativity on the basis of intuition, illumination and revelation.

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